

AN APPROACH TO KEYBOARDING SKILLS: A PANACEA FOR SPEED AND ACCURACY

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ABSTRACT

Keyboarding is an essential skill. Keyboarding is a life long skill. It has evolved from a transcription typing skill where secretaries typed handwritten letters into a generative typing skill involving composing original thought at the keyboard. The paper discusses the various strategies for attaining skills in keyboarding. Among these strategies is proper keyboarding, blank keyboard techniques, and the cognitive mode. The paper concluded by stressing that Speed and Accuracy in data entry are achieved through keyboarding skills. The paper recommended that teachers of keyboarding should insist on proper techniques and continual assessment of students' performance.

KEYWORDS: Mastering keyboards, key strokes, economics, speed and accuracy, correct hand placement, keyboarding techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Mastering keyboarding involves more than just learning the locations of keys. The foundation for masterful keyboarding is technique. Technique involves the positioning and action of the body and fingers as the student is keyboarding. Ergonomics is an important aspect of keyboarding that students need to learn from the beginning of their keyboarding instruction. Learning key location involves a sequential process beginning with letters followed by punctuation, numbers, and symbols. Mastery develops through practice.

Effective and efficient keyboarding begins with learning proper technique. Students should be provided with models of keyboarders assuming good posture as they type. Key stroking is more than pressing keys. According to Bangart (1993), rapid keyboarding requires that the keys are addressed with a quick finger-action. If the finger-action is quick, then keyboarding speed will increase as the time between keystrokes is reduced. Speed and accuracy are built upon well-developed technique, which should be taught at the beginning and then developed through on-going reinforcement. On-going reinforcement of technique is a challenge for teachers because it requires them to be ever-vigilant so that they can recognize and reward proper technique in the classroom or lab.

Keyboarding is a life long skill. It has evolved from a *transcription* typing skill where secretaries typed handwritten letters into a *generative* typing skill involving composing original thought at the keyboard (Cooper, 1983). Student writing develops faster through word processing because it facilitates the review and revision learning process. Efficient keyboarding skills allow students to emphasize concept development instead of focusing on key location efficiently through well-developed keyboarding skills. According to Johnson (2002) "Keyboarding is the penmanship of the computer age." Similarly, Nelson (2000) asserted that, as a fundamental skill in today's society, keyboarding provides our connection with the rest of the world through electronic communication. Students who become efficient keyboarders "compose better, are prouder of their work, produce documents with a neater appearance, and have better motivation". The paper is organized into headings and each heading discusses a specific strategy for developing keyboarding skills.

Rapid Finger-Action

Effective and efficient keyboarding begins with learning proper technique. Students should be provided with models of keyboarders assuming good posture as they type. More specifically, correct hand placement should be demonstrated and explicitly discussed. This should be followed by instruction on proper keystroking. Keystroking is more than pressing keys. Rapid keyboarding requires that the keys are addressed with a quick finger-action. If the finger-action is quick, then keyboarding speed will increase as the time between keystrokes is reduced. According to Erthal (2006) speed and accuracy are built upon well-developed technique, which should be taught at the beginning and then developed through on-going reinforcement. On-going reinforcement of technique is a challenge for teachers because it requires them to be ever vigilant so that they can recognize and reward proper technique in the

classroom or lab. The Type to Learn 4 software supports teachers in teaching proper technique by providing visual and auditory instruction finger striking techniques.

Proper Use of Keyboard

Of all the approaches to keyboarding, it does not matter what approach is used to teach the keyboard. A home row approach, a skip-around approach, a strong-finger-first approach, or whatever, all produce similar results. What is important, however, is that the keyboard should be used in such a way as to provide an opportunity for students to key sentences as early as possible. Keying sentences permits transfer of learning to later sequences, develops chains more quickly, and provides better motivation. If students at the end of the first day of class can key "It is I.", there is considerably more motivation than if they leave the classroom being able to type "its" (Crews, 1983).

Blank Keyboard Techniques

One approach is to say, "As soon as possible, try to key that sentence without watching the keyboard." However, techniques, which prohibit students from watching the keyboard, are detrimental, rather than helpful, to learning. Thus, using typewriters with blank keyboards, putting tape on the keys to cover them, blindfolding students, taping a sheet of paper over the top of the typewriter so that the keys cannot be seen, etc., are all detrimental to learning. In addition, there appear to be few reasons for using keyboard charts. They are primarily useful only to point out the fingering of keys during keyboard learning.

According to Troutner (1983), if students can find the key more quickly by looking directly at the keyboard, contiguity is developed, thereby looking at the keyboard and not at a chart. The teacher needs to consider why students watch the keyboard. There are two possible explanations: either the students have developed a bad habit or they have not yet developed sufficient kinesthetic feedback. If the latter is the case, then the most effective technique to be used in the classroom is to provide the students with lots of practice so that chains can be developed and kinesthetic feedback strengthened. If the former is the case, then speed-forcing techniques are needed to break students of such habits. Drill materials are available for the implementation of such techniques.

Ergonomics

An important part of learning technique is learning ergonomically sound behaviors that support proper body posture and placement. It is important for students (and teachers) to learn and follow these guidelines. Once students have an ergonomically sound foundation and have learned about the proper way to tap the keys, only then can they work to achieve their maximum efficiency in keyboarding. West (2008) discovered that "A series of international studies found that 'up to 60% of the students across the globe reported eye strain, neck and shoulder pain, wrist and back discomfort, headaches and fatigue.'" Posture patterns begin developing as young as seven years old so it is imperative that students are taught the proper way to sit when keyboarding.

According to Wetzel (2001) proper ergonomics is achieved in typewriting through the following techniques:

Students should rest their eyes by looking away from the screen and blinking rapidly while focusing on distant objects approximately every 15 minutes to reduce eyestrain.

A rest from typing should be taken at least every 30 minutes. Students should use different muscles relaxation during the break.

Key Locations techniques

Keyboarding is a psychomotor activity that needs to be taught through introduction, repetition, and reinforcement. Key letter locations should be introduced two at a time in a sequential format with repetitive activities that begin to build the kinesthetic memory traces that will link each letter with the appropriate finger movement and key. According to Erickson, (1999), these activities must be designed to guide the learner toward successful completion and reinforce accomplishment.

In Key location techniques, each lesson begins with a warm up review, where students practice the home row to locate their home base and prepare for the lesson's exercises. Once students are warmed up, the Security Check provides an opportunity to practice all of the letters learned so far by typing character clusters and words. New keys are then introduced, following a pattern of using the same fingers on either hand. These new keys are practiced alone and then through a series of lesson exercises using the other keys learned so far. According to Bernazza (2002), exercises provide varying levels of scaffolding and instruction, such as:

- hints as to which side of the keyboard the character is on,
- hands on a lettered reference keyboard to provide guidance when incorrect keys are pressed,
- presenting full lines of text so students can discover a comfortable typing rhythm,
- instruction for typing letter combinations.

Letter Combinations Techniques

Facility with letter combinations is the key to rapid keying. Leonord (1998) proposed that mastering digraphs (two-letter combinations) was the key to maximum typing speed and accuracy. This aligns with earlier research showing that expert typists were greatly facilitated when typing text that contained "frequent letter combinations or common words," (Fendrick, 1999). For example, the common word "me" can be considered two single letters, "m" and "e". The keyboarder must read the letter "m", identify that the right index finger must be used to type the "m", and then send the command to the finger to type it. The same process is used to type the "e" using the left middle finger. If, however, the word "me" is considered a single unit that requires using the right index and left middle fingers, then the processing time to type it is reduced. This process of "chunking" letter combinations together works well with blends like "th" or "at" as well. As a student becomes more proficient in keyboarding, the task becomes one of keying letter groups rather than single letters and the processing time is thereby dramatically shortened. According to Bartholome (1998), this means that keyboarding mastery will be augmented when digraphs, frequent letter combinations, and common words are taught to students as units. This decreases response time and improves keyboarding speed (Zeitz, 2005).

Three Phases Techniques

The development of keyboarding skills is a cumulative process. New skills must be introduced in a consistent sequence that builds upon previously learned skills. Crews (2006) describes three stages of learning keyboarding skills that student should undergo. These three stages include: Cognitive Phase (Key Introduction), Associative Stimulus Phase (Kinesthetic Memory Traces), and Autonomous Muscle Response Phase (Automaticity). Bloom (1986) supports this sequence of learning for touch-typing.

The Cognitive Phase (Key Introduction):

This initial stage involves the students deliberately thinking about the rules of technique (body, arm, and hand position; keystroking; and ergonomics). The beginning typist is also consciously thinking about the position of each individual key. Entering lines of text involves seeing, processing, and tapping strings of characters separated periodically by spaces. Learners are also purposely working to accomplish key combinations like the proper use of shift keys. In this phase, it is important to introduce the keys in a sequence that will foster student success. The learner's progression while learning the keyboard should be a cumulative process. Pairings of characters should be introduced together with sufficient practice activities in a variety of contexts to afford the learner a certain amount of mastery before moving to the next set of keys. The next lesson should introduce a new set of characters and provide fresh practice activities that incorporate the first set of characters as well as the newly learned keys. This collective process should be continued throughout the entire keyboard.

Associative Stimulus Phase (Kinesthetic Memory Traces):

On-going practice through exercises and activities that are of high interest, high motivation, and high activity can motivate learners to engage in the repetition necessary for "kinesthetic memory traces" to develop. Through this process, students learn to connect the recognition of the character with the action of striking the corresponding key. Developing kinesthetic memory traces is part of the psychomotor learning process (Starr, 2001).

This stage of learning is the longest of the phases and involves developing a sense of continuity and rhythm in keyboarding. Continuity is cultivated through practicing and mastering common character combinations and words,

and acquiring the aforementioned kinesthetic memory traces. Rhythm is developed through a steady repetition of keystrokes. At this stage, accuracy is not as important as speed and rhythm. Support during this phase could begin with a consistent rhythm as with a metronome. However, as the learner masters keyboarding an individualized rhythm will naturally develop based upon how the student addresses groups of letters, rather than from an external musical beat.

Autonomous Muscle Response Phase (Automaticity):

The goal of teaching keyboarding is to familiarize students with the keyboard to a point where they develop automaticity (Bloom, 1986). Automaticity is a level of proficiency where the learner is able to complete a task as a whole without devoting attention to each individual component task. Keyboarding automaticity requires facility in typing to the point where the operator is keying without thinking of the individual keys. In fact, if an accomplished keyboarder tries to think about what each finger is doing, "the entire typing process would collapse,"

Motivation as a Technique

Motivation has a great deal to do with novelty, excitement, and challenge. Prolonged activities will bore learners into inaction. While all students tend to be drawn to computer-based activities, these activities also need to be interesting and provide feedback about students' rates of progress to retain their interest. According to Bartholome (1998), students learn best when they have immediate indications of their ongoing success. Such immediate feedback of results supports performance and serve as a motivation to learning. Activities should be challenging but not overwhelming. This means that students will perform best if the activities are presented at their individual skill levels. According to Troutner (1983), matching the tasks' requirements with the learners' skills makes the learning experience more enjoyable. It is important that students feel a sense of accomplishment as they master the keyboard. The most effective challenges are ones where the expected level of accomplishment rises as the learner's skill levels improve.

The Techniques of Practice

Practice, Practice, Practice! One cannot develop keyboarding skills unless one is willing to practice, starting with the basic keystroke patterns. Students develop motor reflex patterns that enable their fingers to strike the correct keys automatically perfecting keyboarding skills requires a great deal of practice. The goal of learning to keyboard is to develop automaticity in the learner's keyboarding skills. This level of expertise is not seen until one is keyboarding at least 40 WPM. Such proficiency requires persistence and long-term practice in the typical school classroom or computer lab. The use all of the fingers while in practice. If students only use two or three of their ten fingers to type, then they are setting for a disaster. Computer keyboarding practice is not unlike piano keyboarding practice. Students must utilize all of their fingers. The thumbs will be relegated primarily to the space bar, while the bulk of typing will take place with the ring, middle, and index fingers.

Transcription vs Generative keyboarding Techniques

Learning to keyboard using a software package can be quite successful, but will it translate to the "real world?" In most software, students read or hear words that they then key into the computer as quickly and accurately as possible. Nevertheless, how will this process of reading and typing text translate into their lives where most keyboarding time involves original composition. Crew (1983) describes a distinction between transcription and generative keyboarding. *Transcription keyboarding* is the style of keyboarding used in most tutorials where a passage of text is presented to the learner to be keyed into the program or word processing document.

Generative keyboarding identifies the style of keyboarding where one generates original text at the computer. Generative keyboarding is now the predominate form of computing so it is important that skills learned through a transcription method will transfer into a generative world. Wetzel (2001) identifies behavioral transfer like keyboarding as *low-road transfer*. They found that low-road transfer is facilitated through automatization and varied practice.

Automatization is the result of extensive practice, whereby the skill being practiced becomes fast and effortless. New environments or conditions do not adversely affect the level of transfer because the behavior is executed

automatically, regardless of the situation. Crews, (1983) say that automaticity, and by extension skill transfer, is not certain until one is keyboarding at least 50 WPM. Varied practice describes practice that occurs in a variety of contexts. This, too, facilitates low-road skill transfer. Performing a behavior in multiple situations requires one to adapt to subtle differences in those contexts. Considering the level of keyboarding sophistication necessary to reach automatization, varied practice is the method of choice to facilitate transfer from transcription to generative keyboarding, and from the world of a software application to real-world typing situations. It only requires the instructional program to place the learner in a variety of original composition situations to provide transferable experiences to later situations.

Technique of Keyboard mastery

Students should not look at the keyboard – not even a quick peek! Students should look directly at the screen. Students can easily find the starting position without looking at the keyboard by feeling the bumps on the letters ‘F’ and ‘J’ (at the bottom of the key). In the beginning, students will be practicing with letters that do not spell out any words. As students get to know the keys, they will use “real” words and sentences. That is the only way to really be successful when learning to type. Teachers should aim to measure their students typing speed periodically – with the appropriate tools, teachers can check students’ progress in both speed and accuracy. The number of words per minute indicates students typing level. Typing games are a fun way to improve students typing speed and accuracy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Efficient keyboarding skills clear the path toward effective expression. Learning to keyboard accurately and efficiently requires more than being taught location of the characters on the keyboard. It requires a sequential strategy that integrates technique with key location and encourages a great deal of practice to build the automatic skills for transcribing ideas onto the computer screen. Keyboarding instruction succeeds based upon content, pedagogy, and individualization. Schools should offer opportunities for keyboarding contests, and teachers should encourage keyboarding contests among their students.

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